

Appendix S5. Reaction norms of family means between greenhouse and field environments for all traits.

Figure S1: Reaction norms of family means between the two environments for (A) leaf number, (B) height in centimetres, (C) inflorescence number, and (D) silique number (fecundity). The blue colour represents the field environment while the green represents the greenhouse environment.